

WP6 Guide 2 - Collaboration with global VOD providers

August 22, 2025

Version 1.1 / Marius Øfsti & Jakob Isak Nielsen

Guide 2 - Collaboration with global VOD providers

Executive summary

This guide examines the potential and the challenges to collaboration between large US-based global SVoD services and European film producers. The study is part of the CresCine project, which aims to enhance the international competitiveness of smaller European film markets.

The research objectives focus on identifying how the relation between global SVoDs and European producers and distributors is evolving and the key factors in the interaction between them. The recent reduction in investments from the global SVoDs into European productions has increased the importance of output deals for catalog titles and prior relations for commissioned titles. This increases the challenges for smaller producers and distributors in the home entertainment market in general.

Key findings from the research highlight that the global SVoDs offer unique opportunities for selected titles but at the same time there is a vast imbalance in the negotiations. This imbalance is question of economy but even more so about an imbalance in access to relevant information. This makes it difficult for producers to maximize their revenue potential in their relations with the global SVoDs.

The document concludes with recommendations for policy measures that can give European producers more insight and leverage in negotiations with the global SVoDs. This includes better access to information and improving chances for domestic success and building capital.

Recommendations

1. **Reduce information gap:** Independent producers can reduce the information gap by using distributors, sales agents and contract lawyers that have more experience in dealing with global SVoDs as intermediaries. Policy measures can address the information balance by obliging global SVoDs to share viewing numbers on a market-by-market basis. This is common practice in the theatrical window and allows producers and distributors to understand the market and the value of comparable titles.

2. **Adapt to the local strategies of the global SVoDs.** Globally oriented SVoDs such as Netflix, Amazon, HBO Max, Apple, Disney (and Sky Showtime) are not uniform, and their strategies vary between markets. Producers should bring projects to the global SVoDs that fit the SVoDs profile and needs. For fiction features this in most cases leave Netflix as the most likely potential partner and only based on their domestic user base. Producers cannot expect a big payout from streamers, but a low-risk way of realizing otherwise impossible projects.
3. **Increase value of domestic content for global SVoDs:** Policies that require investments from global SVODs proven to be effective in getting global SVoDs to acquire local titles for a domestic audience in markets where the streamers would otherwise not invest. Production incentives tailored to investments from global SVODs or continued engagement in local production (e.g. Spain) can make investment deals more attractive. Policy measures that strengthen domestic theatrical infrastructure will also potentially increase leverage given that domestic theatrical success is the key indicator of value in all subsequent markets.
4. **Build scale and capital:** Our data suggest that both investment deals and licensing deals with global SVoDs are more likely to go to production companies that are vertically integrated with or have a close relation to the larger domestic distributors. As global SVoDs have also proven to make quick and drastic decisions regarding both individual titles and markets, relying on SVoD production alone is also a risk. Producers should seek to combine cost-plus productions with projects that can build long-term capital. Better capitalized companies have more time to weigh options in any negotiation and are also better suited to carefully consider the long-term value of their rights versus the low risk offers of cost-plus funding. Policy measures that allow European producers to build scale and capital would also strengthen their negotiation position against the global SVoDs.

Introduction

This guide is produced in the framework of CresCine, a Horizon Europe-funded project aimed at boosting the European film industry's international competitiveness and cultural diversity, with a particular focus on small markets. Running from 1 March 2023 to 28 February 2026, this 36-month initiative is part of a broader EU effort to enhance the global presence of European filmmaking, alongside two other Horizon-funded projects: SCENE, which integrates cutting-edge technology with sustainability and social responsibility, and REBOOT, focusing on youth engagement and VOD platform development.

The main objective of CresCine is to transform small European film markets by developing targeted research, conducting pilot projects, and generating actionable insights that can drive the sector's growth. The project's scope covers a wide range of key areas: the overall state of the market, audience analysis, sustainability (greening), skills development, distribution, and exhibition, as well as financing and innovation. Through collaboration with over 28 academic and industry organizations—ranging from academic researchers to influential industry players – CresCine will produce State of the Industry reports, detailed datasets, and strategic recommendations. Additionally, the project will host industry sessions at major film festivals, providing valuable platforms to discuss findings and drive forward policy and market innovation.

By piloting its research outcomes in seven European markets, CresCine seeks to empower small markets, enhance their global competitiveness, and contribute to the diversity of cinema in Estonia, Lithuania, Denmark, Ireland, Belgium (Flanders), Croatia, and Portugal.

Scope & Objectives

The entry of US-based global SVoD (Subscription-on-demand-video) services into the European markets has had a significant impact on the film and television industries across the region. Their relative strengths differ between markets, as do their market penetration and usage compared to domestic players. The catalogues of the services also vary between the markets. Despite their global reach, these services are therefore also in various ways adapted to local markets, which affects how they interact with the local industries.

The immediate impact of the global SVoDs entry into the markets has been a reconfiguration of home entertainment value – perhaps initially a net loss. While the DVD sales were in many markets already declining, this was accelerated by streaming services (Øfsti, 2023a). One result of this was the loss of capital reserves among production companies that could not replace the lost home entertainment revenue (Deloitte, 2013). Distributors have also reported that acquiring quality independent films has become more difficult as they face competition from streamers that buy global rights (Øfsti, 2023b).

In this context, this guide explores key lessons learned from expert interviews with European producers and distributors, theatrical release data and VOD catalog presence data provided by the European Audiovisual Observatory, and existing research. We examine 1) what kinds of deals are offered, 2) how deals are made, 3) what the value propositions of these different deals offer producers.

As part of Work Package 6 dedicated to Platforms, Distribution, Exhibition, and Promotion, this guide contributes to helping stakeholders and professionals better understand the various factors at play in the negotiations between the global SVoD services and the European producers.

Structure of the Report

The guide starts with the methodology which provides an overview of the research design and methods used. The next section gives a brief overview of how the global SVoDs are impacting small European markets, and the various deals between producers and the global SVoDs that we have identified. The key lessons summarize the main insights learned from the interviews and data analysis and form the basis of the conclusion and the policy and business recommendations.

Methodology

Qualitative expert interviews

For this guide we conducted eight interviews with experts working within production and distribution across Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Lithuania, Croatia, Ireland and the UK. These

represent companies that range from the individual independent producers to larger vertically integrated companies. Interviewees represent companies and organizations that have had experience selling films, negotiating distribution deals and/or producing films for global SVoD services. Many of the interviewees also have substantial international experience, e.g. working with partners outside the market in which they are currently situated.

- Helene Aurø, ReInvent (Denmark)
- Jamie D'Alton, Motive/Diffusion (Ireland, UK)
- Kestutis Drazdauskas, Artbox (Lithuania)
- Lars Bjørn Hansen, SF Studios (Denmark)
- Claus Toksvig Kjær, Nørlum Entertainment (Denmark)
- Jarle Namtvedt, Ymer Media (Norway)
- Ivor Siber, JUČER (Croatia)
- Julia Short, Independent consultant (UK)

In addition, we consulted the transcripts of eight interviews with European film distributors conducted for the CresCine publication [Release Windows in Post-COVID Film Distribution](#) (Hammoud et al., 2025).

Quantitative data

In addition to the qualitative interviews, we have also examined quantitative data on VoD presences and performance related to theatrical performance and distributors. From Lumiere Pro we have admissions and theatrical distributors of films released in Europe. From (Bengesser et al., 2025) we have a dataset on VoD presence of European titles based on several Lumiere VOD snapshots. Finally, we have examined data on performance released by Netflix in their local top 10 lists as well as the overall global performance in the engagement reports.

The impact of global VoDs across small European markets

Initially, the engagement from Netflix and the other services with local industries was limited. In some cases, they launched with some domestic titles acquired through deals with distributors (Øfsti, 2014), while in other markets they still lack any domestic titles. NRK/Netflix

co-production *Lilyhammer* (2012) was an early example of their involvement in productions beyond licensing (Sundet, 2017) and HBO also at this early stage showed interest in co-financing original European series (Nielsen, 2016). However, it was not until 2017-2018 that streamer spending on European original scripted content really started to pick up (Fontaine, 2024). Investments were initially primarily oriented towards serial fiction. A EAO report based on data from Ampere Analysis estimates that streamer spending on films slowly started to pick up in 2020 and grew substantially across 2021-2023 following a growth trajectory similar to the spending on tv series, constantly representing approximately 10-12% of the overall spending on original scripted content from 2020 to 2023.

Spending on original non-scripted productions (including documentary) follows a trajectory similar to feature film spending. However, scripted productions (tv fiction and fiction film) have consistently represented between 80-88% of the over-all spending with a slightly decreasing share from 2019 to 2023. (Fontaine 2024, p. 27). Spending on original productions has been unevenly distributed across European markets and the importance of the streamer investments relative to broadcaster investments into original productions is also very different across Europe. Streamer investment into original productions in 2023 stands out as having a larger share relative to broadcaster investment particularly in Spain and Italy, but also in the UK (Fontaine 2024).

There are also significant differences between the overall subscriptions and the market share of the global SVoDs across European countries (Bengesser, 2024, EAO Yearbook data). In some markets, such as Denmark, some of the global SVoDs have a relatively high number of subscribers while also facing strong competition from domestic players. In other markets, such as Portugal, the number of subscribers is also relatively high, but the global SVoDs are mainly competing with each other. Finally in markets such as Lithuania the domestic players have significantly stronger positions than the global SVoDs while the overall subscription numbers remain low. The position of the various global SVoDs also differs between the markets. While Netflix remains strong across all markets, the market share of other services such as HBO Max, Amazon Prime, and YouTube Premium varies dramatically between countries. This

impacts both the value of the domestic market for the various SVoDs as well as the need for domestic content to compete against local players.

Consequently, *some* production communities in *some* European markets saw significant investments from the streaming services as they both started acquiring and commissioning domestic titles. This gave some productions options that had not previously existed within small markets, enabling new genres, higher budgets and access to global audiences (Meir & Smits, 2024).

The high volume of new shows, and to a lesser extent films, commissioned by the global SVoDs as well as local services that tried to compete, created a boom in fiction production in some countries, leading up to 2022 (Engelstad, 2024). At that point, Netflix subscriber drops, inflation, price hikes and other circumstances suggested that the streamer investment boom was over or petering out - also for European original content. This is only partially visible in the numbers for 2023 that still demonstrates an over-all increase in total streamer investment into original content. Data on investments for 2024 is not yet available on a pan-European scale, but many sources point at a downturn of investments and a significant squeeze on expenditure for the original productions that are funded. The global streamers as well as their local and regional competition scaled down production or moved out of selected territories all together, most notably HBOs abrupt exit from several small markets following the merger between Warner Bros. and Discovery in 2022.

According to our informants, this has coincided with a less aggressive acquisition strategy, where the global SVoDs are increasingly relying on output deals with a small number of distributors to local content libraries. This sentiment is corroborated by our quantitative analysis that shows that the majority of titles in the Netflix, Amazon, and Disney+ catalogues are acquired from one or two distributors within each territory. These output deals are often with companies that also are vertically integrated with production (Meir, 2024; Øfsti, 2023b). The result of these developments is a market that, on the one hand, offers producers new possibilities and a way to reach audiences far beyond the theatrical model for selected titles.

On the other hand, this makes it increasingly difficult to generate any meaningful revenue outside the theatrical market without an output deal.

What kinds of deals exist?

Deals are either made as a part of the financing plan of the film or after the film is produced. We broadly define all deals made before production as investment deals, and deals made after production as license deals. Further, deals are either exclusive or non-exclusive, and they are either global and in (close to) perpetuity or they are for a limited amount of time and/or a limited number of markets (Meir & Mitric, 2025). In some cases, we can also talk about hybrid-models. These are essentially global exclusives that have a specific exception, often a theatrical release or an exception for the domestic market.

These factors greatly impact the value of the deal. Limited non-exclusive licensing deals are less valuable in the short term but come on top of other revenue sources and do not limit the downstream value. Globally exclusive in (close to) perpetuity deals do not allow any further revenue and therefore have to cover all costs of the film, as well as any potential back end. From a producers' perspective, these deals can be negotiated directly with the global SVoD, through an intermediary such as a sales agent, or indirectly by making deals with a distributor who in turn has or makes a deal with the global SVoD. Typically, investment deals will be negotiated by the producers as a part of the financing, while sales agents and distributors are more often involved in the licensing deals.

	Commissioned	Global acquisition	Hybrid	Exclusive license	Non-exclusive license
Rights	Globally exclusive in close to perpetuity, including derivative works.	Globally exclusive in close to perpetuity.	Globally exclusive with specific exception (theatrical/domestic). Length of exclusive window can be 4-5 years or close to perpetuity. Rights to derivative works might be included.	Limited in time (4-5 years), can be global but more often specific territories. Rights to derivative works retained by the producer.	Limited in time (4-5 years), can be global but more often specific territories. Rights to derivative works retained by the producer.
SVoD share of investment	Investment – Fully financed	License - Fully financed	Investment/License – Significant contribution (up to 50%)	License - Limited	License – Very limited
Negotiations	By producer on a project-by-project basis. In most cases there are prior relations.	By producer on a project-by-project basis. In most cases there are prior relations.	By producer and in some cases theatrical distributor on a project-by-project basis. In most cases there are prior relations.	In most cases by distributor or other aggregator as part of output deals or library acquisitions. For producers festivals and partnerships with distributors and aggregators can result in deals.	In most cases by distributor or other aggregator as part of library acquisitions. For producers, festivals and partnerships with distributors and aggregators can result in deals.
Risk and reward	Low risk for producers but no back end and no possibility of independently exploiting IP.	Producer carries risk during production. No performance related risk on release but also no back end. Possibility of independently exploiting IP might be limited.	Limited risk for producer and back end limited to the specific exception. Depending on length of exclusivity and IP transfer further exploration might be possible.	Producer and distributor carry most of the risk but success in theatres results in higher value. Further exploitation of IP rights possible immediately and exploitation of specific work after an exclusive period.	Lower value for each deal but further exploitation is immediately possible.
Value proposition	Full financing of the project ensures production. In some cases, higher budgets than possible with domestic theatrical, global audience reach.	The value of sale is likely higher than for a commissioned title as the producer sells a finished film. Producer investments are recouped quickly and in one sale.	A significant contribution to the financing plan greatly increases chances of production. In some cases, higher budgets than if relying on just (domestic) theatrical. Possible to achieve financial success in the key markets as well as reaching global audiences.	Pre-sales of rights contribute to financing plans, though usually relatively limited in scope. Output deals contribute indirectly as it allows distributors to include licensing to global SVoD when calculating MG offer. Value and reach depend on how many territories are included. Several deals can be combined if exclusive territories don't overlap.	Rarely or never a part of the pre-sales. Requires several deals to be of substantial value, but all revenue is additive and does not restrict further sales. Reach and value of each deal is likely to be limited.

Key Findings

Globally exclusive deals

According to our informants, globally exclusive deals are almost always negotiated on a per-project basis. While this in theory offers opportunities for any project that has a project that is attractive for a streamer, evidence still suggests that access to these deals is also highly relational. Among our informants that had successfully sold exclusive global rights to SVoDs some had an ongoing relationship with one or more streaming services, while others had relied on intermediaries such as distributors to approach the services.

One informant stressed that the key to successful commissioning deals with the global SVoDs was to approach them with projects that were suited for the streamer, and not projects that already had been rejected by the public funding bodies. For this informant the key was to have a stratified slate of productions enabling the company to shift emphasis between productions both for theatrical release, for local broadcasters and global streamers. The cost-plus financed films did not have a huge payout, but the deals were safe bets that made it possible to realize projects that would otherwise not be possible.

On occasion, films from small European markets have generated remarkable viewing figures on global SVoDs such as Netflix. Within CresCine markets, a film such as *Loving Adults* (DK, 2022) has stacked up approximately 124M hours of watching/70M views and *Life is Beautiful* (DK, 2023) approximately 92M hours/55M views.¹ The lion's share of that viewing is generated outside of the home market yet several of our sources insist that not only Netflix but also HBO Max are primarily looking at local performance in local markets. Key metrics include national viewing numbers and completion percentages. By that account, global success is often a welcome bonus rather than an explicit goal and only very few non-English films from small markets, such as *Troll* (NO, 2022), are higher budget films commissioned on the premise of reaching wide global audiences. Consequently, although many producers of non-English titles

¹ This is accumulated self-reported data calculated from Netflix' first five Engagement Reports (all of 2023-2024 and the first half year of 2025) in addition to - in the case of *Loving Adults* (2022) - viewing metrics from Netflix' Top 10-lists. Netflix top 10 data begins from July 4th, 2021. *Loving Adults* did not make the top 10 for non-English films in November or December 2022 so some viewing is missing for the film. The data has been collected from www.whats-on-netflix.com/top-10-title-search/.

would welcome performance-based payouts from the streamers they did not realistically expect this, and global performance metrics would likely not feature prominently in such an arrangement were it to be implemented.

The importance of the domestic market for the streamers was also a factor in one informant's skepticism towards hybrid model deals. Given the remarkable performance of some CresCine feature films in international markets, this would potentially open up avenues for hybrid deals that for instance combine domestic theatrical with international VoD release. However, given that global SVoDs were similarly focused on the domestic market, this tended to work against the logic of such hybrid models. The streamers had a reduced willingness to invest compared to a streaming exclusive title. The interest in the local market from the SVoDs would also cut away at the domestic transactional video-on-demand (TVoD) window which for some titles is still valuable. The availability of films on any digital platform also comes with a piracy risk particularly vulnerable to TVoD. Some informants also reported that hybrid-deals in some cases had a negative impact for distributors and theatres as films that still had meaningful admissions were blocked from further screenings when the exclusive window ended.

Limited licensing deals

Our informants suggest that the global SVoDs are mainly acquiring licensed titles from distributors or other aggregators as a part of packages. This pattern is also confirmed by our data as the majority of theatrical features from the CresCine markets available on global SVoDs were initially released by the larger distributors within each market. The informants describe these packages as either output deals or library deals. Output deals cover upcoming titles, and the value of each title is to a large extent set on the basis of pre-existing criteria, usually theatrical performance. Library deals are one-time deals where a number of titles are acquired. In both cases, the length of deals tends to be four or five years. A single distributor might have several of these deals that are differentiated either by territory or by the age of films.

While our informants argued that the global SVoDs increased reliance on output deals made the home entertainment market more difficult for independent producers, there are still options to consider. Output deals typically come with a number of "slots". In cases where there are

unused slots, they can be open to include recent and upcoming titles from outside producers if the home entertainment rights are not being otherwise exploited. In cases where there are free slots in the deals, they can in some cases include titles from outside producers. For older titles that are not being fully exploited, producers can also approach various aggregators that bundle film rights, often thematically, and sell them to global SVoDs. For distributors, there is also value in building a library of home entertainment rights for domestic titles, as this is the content that the global SVoDs cannot get from other sources (Øfsti 2023).

Negotiations

“You need to work with somebody that has that knowledge of the whole market, it might be a lawyer, or it might be an aggregator. But have somebody that can play bad cop, rather than you as an independent producer negotiating. Lawyers are brilliant.” - Informant

The dynamics of the relations between European producers and distributors and the global SVoDs are fundamentally skewed. Not only are the global SVoDs much bigger companies, at a European level the supply of new films is much higher than the demand and the global SVoDs have the information advantage. This information gap pertains not only to the performance of titles but also on the value of previous acquisitions. As these are always under NDAs, the global SVoDs know what they have paid for everything they acquired, but the sellers only know the price of what they have sold themselves.

The clear advice from our informants was therefore to avoid selling directly to the global SVoDs, at least without the aid of outside counsel such as an experienced lawyer. As distributors, sales agents, aggregators, and lawyers are involved in multiple deals, they are able to have a much better understanding of the value of any given title. This value is most often based on previous sales of titles with comparable casting, genre and so on, rather than the (producers’) expectations of performance. Still, domestic theatrical performance or festival acclaim can be effective as leverage. As in any business deal, a producer that can afford to be patient will be more likely to get a better deal. In the short term, the ability to explore multiple options can greatly increase the value of the offers, even from the initial contact. In a longer-term, having

the financial stability that allows a company to accept a lower initial offer to retain long-term rights has also been shown to be the most profitable long-term strategy in some cases (Meir & Mitric 2025).

Conclusion

For European producers, the various configurations of deals offer different value propositions that must be weighed against each other. For most producers, and especially the smaller ones, money early is worth more than money later. Investments that can be a part of the financing plan greatly increases the chances that any given project is realized. For many producers, staying in production is how the company and salaries are financed. These producers will in many cases be able to fully pre-finance any given project through a combination of public funding and pre-sales. While most of these deals, such as the sale of rights for specific territories, come with profit sharing agreements, they will in many cases not recoup their MGs and as such produce limited downstream revenue (Øfsti 2023a).

In this scenario, a cost-plus type of deal with a global SVoD is very attractive. While these deals remove any possibility of future earnings, many producers are not in the situation where they can bank on these in any case. For the global SVoDs, such producers are also attractive partners as they will in most cases have lower expectations of the “plus” part of the cost-plus equation as their back end, they are giving up is limited. Several informants admitted that they would have accepted cost-plus deals with global SVoDs that would ultimately have been less financially beneficial than producing the film independently. In some cases, the decision to produce independently came after advice from more experienced production partners, in others because there was no interest from the streamers to go beyond the pre-sale of a limited license.

There is also a risk that producers working exclusively on cost-plus deals become stuck in a vicious circle. The cost-plus deals are attractive to producers with limited capital reserves as it allows them to make films, sometimes even with high budgets, but as they do not generate any significant capital they also can't transition into a position where they can afford to take a bigger financial risk in order to reap the long-term rewards.

Our informants and our data also suggest that the home entertainment market is increasingly favoring the larger distributors and others that are able to offer larger libraries or regular supply of titles through output deals. This puts the smaller distributors and producers at a disadvantage in all parts of the process. If only the larger distributors can bank on home entertainment revenue, they can also offer higher acquisition fees in the first place. Similarly, the smaller producers are faced with a considerable information gap regarding previous evaluations when dealing with global SVoDs. In many cases, it will therefore be more valuable in the long term to go with intermediaries to achieve scale, even if that means giving up a share of the revenue.

For most filmmakers, producers included, profitability is rarely the only or even the most important motivation for being in the business. As such, global SVoDs might offer creative opportunities that a traditional theatrical release does not – and vice versa. Similarly, a deal with a global SVoD might offer a significantly larger audience than traditional theatrical distribution, even if it is less profitable. Given the highly transactional and relational nature of the film industry, it is therefore not uncommon to enter into a less than ideal deal because the filmmakers, or the buyers, believe that it can have long-term benefits beyond the economic.

References

Bengesser, C. (2024). Four types of video-on-demand markets: Comparing the development of European VoD. In *Journal of Digital Media & Policy* (Vol. 15, Issue European-Based VoDs: Models, Alternatives and Predictions, pp. 193–212). Intellect.

https://doi.org/10.1386/jdmp_00146_1

Bengesser, C., Øfsti, M., & Trans, M. B. (2025). Assessing the distinctiveness of public service catalogues: A comparison of European content in local, regional and global video-on-demand service. *MedieKultur: Journal of Media and Communication Research*, 40(78), Article 78.

<https://doi.org/10.7146/mk.v40i78.147197>

Deloitte. (2013). *Sundhedstilstanden i dansk spillefilmsproduktion*.

<https://www.dfi.dk/sites/default/files/docs/2018-02/Deloitte-sundhedstilstanden-i-dansk-spillefilmsproduktion.pdf>

EAO Yearbook (2025). “Main OTT SVOD Groups in Europe”, The European Audiovisual Observatory.

Engelstad, A. (2024). Bonanza i dramabransjen. In H. Vibeto, C. Vanebo, & M. Øfsti (Eds), *På innsiden*. Fagbokforlaget. <https://doi.org/10.55669/10.55669/oa420403>

Fontaine, G. (2024). *Audiovisual services spending on original European content–2024 Edition*. European Audiovisual Observatory. <https://rm.coe.int/investments-in-original-european-content-2024-edition-september-2024-q/1680b17ccf>

Hammoud, P., Ranaivoson, H., & Raats, T. (2025). *Release windows in post-covid film Production* (CresCine). <https://www.crescine.eu/release-windows-post-covid>

Meir, C. (2024). Localizing global platforms in Scandinavia and globalizing Scandinavian popular cinema: Netflix, SF Studios and the contemporary Nordic film industries. *Journal of Scandinavian Cinema*, 14(2), 107–126. https://doi.org/10.1386/jisca_00113_1

Meir, C., & Mitric, P. (2025). *Intellectual Property and the Contemporary European Audiovisual Industries*. <https://www.cepi-producers.eu/post/cepi-unveils-a-new-study-on-intellectual-property-in-the-european-audiovisual-sector>

Meir, C., & Smits, R. (Eds). (2024). *European cinema in the streaming era: Policy, platforms, and production*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Nielsen, J. I. (2016). Points of contact, points of distance: DR / TV 2 meet HBO / Netflix. *Northern Lights*, 14, 29–45. <https://doi.org/10.1386/nl.14.29>

Øfsti, M. (2014). - Lav norskandel en trussel mot norsk film. In *Rushprint* (Vol. 49, Issue 6, pp. 20–21).

Øfsti, M. (2023a). More local, more risky, more studio-like: How Norwegian film distributors adapted their strategies to the streaming age. *Journal of Digital Media & Policy*, 14(3), 339–355. https://doi.org/10.1386/jdmp_00133_1

Øfsti, M. (2023b). *Norway After Netflix. Local Distributor Strategies in a Global Movie Market*. NTNU. <https://ntnuopen.ntnu.no/ntnu-xmlui/handle/11250/3045010>

Sundet, V. S. (2017). Co-Produced Television Drama and the Cost of Transnational ‘Success’: The Making of Lilyhammer. In E. Bakøy, R. Puijk, & A. Spicer (Eds), *Building successful and sustainable film and television businesses: A cross-national perspective*. Intellect.